

SafeCrossLight: Pedestrian-Aware Traffic Light Control using Deep Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—Urban intersections often struggle to balance traffic efficiency with the safety of Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) such as pedestrians. While traditional traffic light control (TLC) methods focus on optimizing vehicle flow, they often neglect pedestrian safety. Therefore, we propose SafeCrossLight, a deep reinforcement learning (DRL) - based approach that aims to address both efficiency and safety in a unified framework. By factoring pedestrians’ safety into the learning process, SafeCrossLight enables a more responsible and adaptive decision-making process at intersections. Our method is evaluated through Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) and compared with several state-of-the-art TLC approaches. Results show that SafeCrossLight significantly reduces unsafe pedestrian behaviors while maintaining strong efficiency in both vehicle and pedestrian flow, suggesting its high potential for real-world deployment in urban traffic systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mitigating traffic congestion and improving safety are two of the most critical challenges faced by urban road junction management [1]. Every year, suboptimal signal timing contributes to billions of dollars in lost economic productivity, while conflicts between vehicles and vulnerable road users (VRUs), especially pedestrians at signalized intersections, lead to serious injuries and fatalities [2]. Thus, it is critical to design traffic light control (TLC) strategies that can maximize traffic throughput and protect VRUs.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the motivation for SafeCrossLight. (A) When pedestrian safety is overlooked, the pedestrian signal may turn red before pedestrians finish crossing and vehicles regain green too early, causing collisions. (B) If pedestrian flow efficiency is ignored, they have to wait their green light for a long time, while little vehicle traffic still has priority. SafeCrossLight aims to avoid both by balancing traffic efficiency and VRUs’ safety.

Traditional TLC methods, such as fixed time control [3] and Webster method [4], focus primarily on vehicle delays and cycle length. They fail to adapt to real-time fluctuations

in traffic flow. Deep reinforcement learning (DRL) has recently become a powerful tool for adaptive signal control because of its ability to learn complex strategies in high-dimensional dynamic environments such as cloud resource allocation [17]. However, most DRL-based controllers only optimize the efficiency of vehicle traffic, either ignoring safety-critical behaviors or importing only a simple “all-red” phase, thus failing to adequately address pedestrian risk. As shown in Fig. 1, neglecting VRUs leads to two main problems: (a) traffic light switching conflict (TSC) and (b) pedestrian accumulation.

In this work, we introduce SafeCrossLight, a DRL Approach that simultaneously optimizes traffic efficiency and pedestrian safety. Our key contributions are:

- Safety-aware state and reward design. We extend the classic TLC state representation with explicit pedestrian features (the number of waiting pedestrians and TSCs) and define a composite reward that penalizes vehicle queues and TSCs.
- Two-stage transition and stable DRL architecture. SafeCrossLight inserts a “pedestrian clearance” phase followed by a “vehicle yellow” phase, which closely mirrors real-world signal operations and reduces conflict opportunities. Besides, we employ Double Deep Q-Network (DQN) with Dueling Network Architecture (D3QN) to reduce Q-value overestimation and focus learning on critical decision states, ensuring stable convergence under high-penalty safety.
- Comprehensive experimental validation. SafeCrossLight outperforms classical baselines (Static-20s [3], Webster [4], MaxPressure [5]) and state-of-the-art DRL methods (IntelliLight [6], SafeLight-R [7]) across both vehicle throughput and pedestrian safety metrics. In a four-way intersection on Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO), compared with Static-20s, SafeCrossLight reduces average vehicle waiting time by over 31%, cuts travel time by 22%. From a pedestrian safety perspective, it also outperforms state-of-the-art DRL baselines, achieving a low TSC rate of 0.10, while SafeLight-R and IntelliLight obtained 0.16 and 0.28, respectively.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Traffic Efficiency Oriented Traditional Approaches

Traditional TLC methods aim to optimize vehicular flow in urban environments. Early implementations, such as static-20s [3], employ fixed-cycle signal plans where each phase

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operates for a predetermined duration. Building on this, Webster’s Method [4] introduces a formula-based approach that determines optimal cycle lengths based on critical flow ratios and lost times. More recently, MaxPressure [5] has emerged as a dynamic strategy that selects phases by maximizing the pressure difference between incoming and outgoing queue lengths. However, these methods still rely on predefined rules and cannot fully adapt to complex, time-varying traffic patterns, prompting a shift toward deep reinforcement learning methods.

B. Traffic Efficiency Oriented Deep Reinforcement Learning Approaches

In recent years, DRL has shown great potential in adaptive TLC by significantly improving vehicle delay, queue length, and throughput. PressLight [8] integrates max-pressure theory into a DQN reward to maximise network throughput and minimise travel time, outperforming fixed-time and earlier RL methods on arterial networks. At the single-intersection level, Li et al. [9] employ proximal policy optimisation (PPO) to reduce average vehicle waiting time. Ma et al. [10] introduce an actor-critic framework that uses sequential traffic data to adapt signal timing, which achieves shorter queue lengths and higher throughput compared to prior DRL approaches. For larger scenarios, Chu et al. [11] propose a decentralised advantage actor-critic algorithm, which achieves superior peak-hour performance relative to state-of-the-art multi-agent methods. IntelliLight [6] employs a DQN coupled with a high-dimensional traffic state encoding and a composite reward function integrating queue length, delay ratio, cumulative waiting time, phase-switch frequency, and vehicle throughput. Although these DRL methods perform well in improving vehicle efficiency, they do not address the safety needs of VRUs (such as pedestrians and cyclists).

C. Safety Oriented Deep Reinforcement Learning Approaches

Recent works have begun to incorporate safety objectives into traffic signal RL in various ways. Mueller and Sabatelli [12] restrict the agent’s action set to legally non-conflicting phases and use action masking to prevent unsafe transitions. Han et al. [13] introduce pedestrian delay into the reward function and employ a discrete state encoding for both vehicle and pedestrian queues, achieving substantial reductions in average pedestrian wait time and queue length in SUMO. Du et al. propose the SafeLight [7], which integrates a safety enforcement module with a standard RL agent and applies reward shaping based on the Kullback–Leibler divergence from a hand-crafted safe policy. SafeLight demonstrates fewer simulated collisions while maintaining throughput, and its variant, SafeLight-R, further reduces collision risk by penalising unsafe action distributions. Despite these advances, these methods do not explicitly address the TSC issues (Fig.1.a), thereby failing to address this critical safety risk.

III. PROPOSED METHOD: SAFECROSSLIGHT

SafeCrossLight emphasizes a more holistic observation space, safety-aware reward design, and realistic signal con-

trol transitions to better reflect real-world intersection dynamics.

The agent of SafeCrossLight DRL framework refers to a traffic light signal controller which is typically hosted on an edge server. In reality, the agent collects the DRL state data as shown in Fig. 2 via deployed cameras with the help of advanced computer vision technologies for object detection. The agent performs action to switch the traffic light phase to the next or not, calculate reward value, then store those DRL trajectory (a sequence of state, action, and reward) data. Periodically, edge servers from multiple junctions will send those collected trajectory data to the central cloud server for DRL model training. The updated model will be then distributed to different regions or junctions for inference.

Fig. 2. The DRL agent of SafeCrossLight interacts with the urban road junction environment by observing the current state, taking actions to switch traffic signal phases, and receiving a reward based on traffic efficiency and pedestrian safety.

At each time step, the agent:

- 1) Observes the current state S_t from SUMO (signal phase, vehicle queues, pedestrian queues, and violations, etc.);
- 2) Selects an action a_t (hold or switch) using the D3QN;
- 3) If switching, executes a two-stage transition (pedestrian clearance then vehicle yellow) before the next green phase;
- 4) Advances the simulation for a fixed interval, receives reward R_t balancing efficiency and safety, and records (S_t, a_t, R_t, S_{t+1}) into replay memory.

A. Agent Design

1) *State*: Our state space design builds upon traditional TLC environments but introduces additional features to explicitly account for VRU safety.

In the literature, the state vector typically includes:

- Current traffic light phase represented as a one-hot vector;
- The number of vehicles waiting in each incoming lane.

We preserve these elements while extending the state to model vulnerable road user behavior. Let n denote the number of main incoming directions or approaches at the intersection (e.g., $n = 4$ for a standard four-way junction). The complete state vector $S_t \in \mathbb{R}^{5n}$ at time step t includes the following components:

- $\mathbf{p}_t \in \{0, 1\}^n$: One-hot encoding of the current main traffic light phase.
- $\mathbf{v}_t \in \mathbb{R}^n$: Number of waiting vehicles on each of the four incoming vehicle lanes.
- $\mathbf{w}_t \in \mathbb{R}^n$: Number of pedestrians in the four designated waiting corner near the crosswalks.
- $\mathbf{c}_t \in \mathbb{R}^n$: Number of pedestrians currently crossing under any light condition.
- $\mathbf{r}_t \in \mathbb{R}^n$: Number of pedestrians currently crossing under the TSC conflict.

The full state vector is therefore constructed as:

$$S_t = ([\mathbf{p}_t \ \mathbf{v}_t \ \mathbf{w}_t \ \mathbf{c}_t \ \mathbf{r}_t])^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{5n} \quad (1)$$

2) *Action*: The action space defines the discrete set of decisions available to the DRL agent at each time step. In this study, the agent controls traffic signals at an intersection by either maintaining the current phase or initiating a transition to the next main phase.

Formally, the action space is defined as:

$$A_t = \{0, 1\} \quad (2)$$

where:

- 0: Maintain the current traffic signal phase.
- 1: Initiate a transition to the next main phase in the predefined phase list.

This action setting is consistent with many previous DRL-based traffic control frameworks such as SafeLight [7] and PressLight [8], where the agent is given binary control: to hold or switch the current phase. However, in most previous works, switching is implemented either instantly or with a fixed all-red buffer. These designs can lead to unrealistic or unsafe transitions, especially in pedestrian-rich intersections.

A core innovation of our method lies in the design of multi-step transition logic when switching from one phase to another. As Fig. 3 illustrates, when the agent chooses 1, the environment does not immediately switch to the next green phase. Instead, it inserts two transitional phases between the current and target main phases to ensure a safer and more realistic signal change:

- 1) *Pedestrian clearance phase*: First, all pedestrian green signals are switched to red, giving time for any remaining vulnerable users to finish crossing.
- 2) *Vehicle yellow phase*: Then, any vehicle lanes currently with green signals are changed to yellow to warn of the upcoming stop, following real-world traffic conventions.

This balance of safety and efficiency in phase transitions is critical in mixed-traffic environments, especially when VRUs are involved.

3) *Reward*: The reward function guides the agent toward a balance of overall traffic efficiency and pedestrian safety. At each time step t , we compute:

$$R_t = -\left(\sum_{\text{dirs}} V_{t,\text{dir}} + 0.5 \sum_{\text{dirs}} P_{t,\text{dir}} + 2 \sum_{\text{dirs}} C_{t,\text{dir}}\right) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3. Two-stage transition illustration: transition from Phase 1 to Phase 2 via a two-stage process - (1) a pedestrian-clearance phase turns all pedestrian greens to red, then (2) a vehicle-yellow phase switches current vehicle greens to yellow before activating the next green phase.

where:

- $V_{t,\text{dir}}$: number of waiting vehicles on incoming lane “dir” at time t .
- $P_{t,\text{dir}}$: number of pedestrians in the designated waiting corner for direction “dir” at time t .
- $C_{t,\text{dir}}$: number of pedestrians currently crossing under TSCs in direction “dir” at time t .

The weight allocation is based on following considerations:

- A heavier penalty for TSC ($w_3 = 2.0$) is used to drive the agent away from unsafe phase switches, promoting safety-oriented policies.
- Pedestrian waiting time is assigned a lower weight ($w_2 = 0.5$) because it contributes less to intersection-level congestion, but still affects pedestrian commuting efficiency.
- Vehicle waiting ($w_1 = 1.0$) is used as the baseline, as reducing vehicle queues remains a fundamental goal in traffic signal optimization.

This weighted design helps the agent prioritize VRUs safety without sacrificing vehicular efficiency, and helps the agent learn a balanced control strategy that is appropriate for urban intersections involving a mix of traffic participants.

The reward function of many existing work is primarily designed for vehicle throughput. For example, PressLight [8] uses vehicle delay or queue length as the sole reward signal, ignoring pedestrians altogether. IntelliLight [6] focuses on minimizing waiting time for vehicles, with no mechanism to model or penalize red-light violations or waiting pedestrians.

In contrast, our design explicitly distinguishes between: traffic efficiency indicators (the number of waiting vehicles and pedestrians), and safety indicator (TSC), giving the agent both mobility and safety supervision in its learning signal.

B. DRL Algorithm

The DRL architecture of our SafeCrossLight is based on D3QN. The Double DQN component decreases the overestimation bias of standard DQN, which is critical for avoiding premature signal changes that could endanger pedestrians. The dueling network separates state-value and advantage estimation, allowing the agent to generalize in routine traffic conditions while focusing learning on states where the balance between vehicular flow and pedestrian safety is most critical. These improvements jointly achieve more stable and efficient learning in complex intersection control scenarios.

IV. EVALUATION METHODOLOGY

A. Simulation Platform Settings

We used SUMO version 1.12.0 [15] for this experiment and implemented our DRL agent using RLlib under the Ray framework [16].

B. Parameter Setting

The hyperparameters used in our DRL framework are listed in Table I. These parameters were selected based on preliminary experiments and best practices in DRL for TLC.

TABLE I
HYPERPARAMETER SETTINGS USED IN THE EXPERIMENT.

Parameter	Initial Value
Action size	4
Batch size	64
Discount factor (γ)	0.95
Random probability (ϵ)	0.01
Greedy factor	0.01
Episode	300
Number of environments	4
Experience pool capacity	20,000

These parameters were chosen to balance exploration and exploitation during training, ensure stable learning, and optimize traffic flow while minimizing pedestrian delays.

C. Road Network Topology

The road network used in this experiment is a 1x1 four-way intersection designed for TLC. This intersection represents a typical urban road scenario where vehicles and pedestrians interact under a controlled traffic signal system.

1) *Intersection Structure*: The intersection consists of four main roads in the north, south, east, and west directions. Each road has a total length of 150 meters and contains:

- Two lanes per direction: One lane for straight-going traffic and another for left or right turns.
- Pedestrian crosswalks: Clearly marked crosswalks are present on all four sides of the intersection.
- Pedestrian waiting areas: Dedicated spaces where pedestrians wait before crossing.
- A traffic signal system: A central traffic light regulates vehicle movements and pedestrian crossings through multiple signal phases.

The overall spatial layout of the simulated intersection is illustrated in Fig. 4. It clearly shows the position and organization of vehicle lanes, sidewalks, crosswalks, and pedestrian waiting corners, all of which play an important role in traffic control and safety management in our simulation environment.

2) *Traffic Demand Design*: To simulate realistic urban intersection conditions, the traffic demand in our experiment consists of both vehicles and pedestrians. A total of 500 vehicles are distributed across the simulation, departing at regular intervals from multiple directions over the first 1000 seconds. The vehicle inflow is asymmetric, with higher traffic volume from the north and west approaches to represent

Fig. 4. Intersection layout. Vehicle lanes (dark gray) are configured with separate through and turning lanes; pedestrian crosswalks (light gray) span each approach; waiting corners (green) provide dedicated staging areas for pedestrians before crossing; and sidewalks (olive) border all roads.

typical main-road traffic patterns, and lighter flow from the east and south to simulate secondary roads.

Meanwhile, 3600 pedestrians are generated uniformly throughout the simulation, with one pedestrian entering the network per second. Their departure and destination points are evenly distributed among the four crosswalks of the intersection. This setup allows for a balanced evaluation of both vehicular traffic efficiency and pedestrian safety under various control strategies.

D. Evaluation Metric

To evaluate the effectiveness of the DRL-based TLC system, we use several key metrics that assess traffic efficiency and pedestrian safety at the intersection.

1) *Traffic Light Switching Conflict Rate (TSCR)*: The traffic light switching conflict rate measures the average number of pedestrians crossing under traffic light switching conflicts per second. This metric is computed as:

$$TSCR = \frac{\text{total_pedestrians_under_TSCs}}{\text{simulation_time}} \quad (4)$$

We express TSCR in seconds so that agents can receive immediate feedback during each simulation step. The lower the TSCR value, the better the pedestrian safety performance at that intersection.

2) *Pedestrian Efficiency Metrics*: To evaluate pedestrian flow efficiency, with all time-based metrics measured in seconds (s), we consider the following two metrics:

- Average Pedestrian Waiting Time (PW): The average duration from the moment a pedestrian arrives at the waiting corner to the moment they receive a green signal permitting them to start crossing. It is calculated as the total waiting time of all pedestrians divided by the number of pedestrians.
- Average Pedestrian Travel Time (PT): The average total duration from the moment a pedestrian is generated in the simulation (at a pedestrian entrance) to the moment they successfully reach their destination across the intersection. It includes both waiting and crossing times, and is similarly averaged across all pedestrians.

Shorter waiting and travel times indicate a more efficient pedestrian crossing system.

3) *Vehicle Efficiency Metrics*: For vehicular traffic, with all time-based metrics measured in seconds (s), we assess intersection efficiency using the following metrics:

- Average Vehicle Waiting Time (VW): The waiting time refers to the accumulated time when a vehicle stops at the red light. VW is calculated as the total waiting time of all vehicles divided by the number of vehicles.
- Average Vehicle Travel Time (VT): The travel time refers to the duration when a vehicle enters and then leaves the junction. VT is averaged across all vehicles.

A well-optimized TLC system should reduce vehicle waiting time while maintaining smooth traffic flow.

E. Compared Methods

Our SafeCrossLight was evaluated against three baseline methods commonly used in traffic signal optimization: Static 20s [3], Webster’s Method [4], Max Pressure [5], and two representative DRL-based approaches: IntelliLight [6] and SafeLight-R [7].

V. EVALUATE RESULTS & ANALYSIS

A. Results of Different Methods

Table II summarizes the performance of each method across the five metrics.

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT TLC METHODS.

BOLD INDICATES BEST VALUE; UNDERLINE INDICATES SECOND-BEST.

Method	PW	PT	VW	VT	TSCR
Static 20s	21.10	132.02	409.37	513.33	0.2110
Webster	21.13	132.05	428.69	529.05	0.4893
Max Pressure	<u>20.52</u>	<u>131.44</u>	299.93	417.88	0.1908
IntelliLight	18.48	121.74	178.93	298.45	0.2837
SafeLight-R	21.83	132.94	319.45	412.68	<u>0.1594</u>
SafeCrossLight	21.65	133.37	<u>279.98</u>	<u>398.82</u>	0.1038

B. Training Convergence

Fig. 5 shows that our proposed SafeCrossLight has been well converged in a fairly steady way after about 65 episodes. Conversely, the competing method SafeLight-R has a clear oscillation despite the achieved convergence around 80 episodes. This demonstrates the conciseness and effectiveness of our DRL framework design especially its reward function.

C. Analysis of Metric Results

The comprehensive evaluation presented in Table II reveals critical insights into the performance of various traffic control strategies under pedestrian–vehicle interaction scenarios.

Fig. 5. The evolution of the average reward per episode for SafeCrossLight and its competing method SafeLight-R during training. Our agent rapidly improves over the first 40 iterations and then stabilizes.

1) *Pedestrian-oriented Analysis*: While the IntelliLight system achieves the shortest average pedestrian waiting time (18.48s), this apparent advantage masks significant safety compromises, as its TSCR is 0.28, which is 172% higher than our method’s 0.10. This difference suggests IntelliLight’s optimization strategy prioritizes immediate pedestrian throughput at the expense of safety regulation compliance. Our methodology maintains pedestrian waiting times at 21.65s, representing a modest 17% increase over IntelliLight but delivering a 63% reduction in dangerous crossing violations. Notably, the pedestrian travel time under our control method (133.37s) remains competitive with static timing approaches (132.02s for Static 20s) while substantially outperforming adaptive methods like Max Pressure (131.44s) in safety-critical metrics. This balance comes from our phased transition design that prevents abrupt signal changes, allowing pedestrians to complete crossings safely without inducing excessive delays.

2) *Vehicle-oriented Analysis*: In the vehicular traffic aspect, our approach’s average waiting time is 279.98s and travel time is 398.82s, outperforming even specialized vehicle-centric controllers. Compared to the Max Pressure algorithm, which is traditionally considered state-of-the-art for vehicle prioritization, our method reduces vehicle waiting time by 6.7% (299.93s vs. 279.98s) while simultaneously improving travel time by 4.6% (417.88s vs. 398.82s). While IntelliLight achieves lower absolute vehicle waiting times (178.93s), this comes at unacceptable safety costs and a 53% higher TSCR compared to our balanced approach.

3) *Safety-oriented Analysis*: The TSCR highlights key differences in how each method addresses pedestrian safety. Our approach achieves the lowest TSCR at 0.10, which is 34.8% lower than SafeLight-R (0.15) and 78.8% lower than IntelliLight (0.28). Traditional methods perform even worse: Webster’s TSCR of 0.49 is over 370% higher than ours.

D. Composite Performance Score

To provide a unified metric for comparing overall performance across efficiency and safety, we define the Composite Performance Score (CPS) as:

$$CPS = \alpha \tilde{P}\tilde{W} + \beta \tilde{P}\tilde{T} + \gamma \tilde{V}\tilde{W} + \delta \tilde{V}\tilde{T} + \epsilon \tilde{T}\tilde{S}\tilde{C}\tilde{R} \quad (5)$$

where $P\tilde{W}$, $\tilde{P}T$, $V\tilde{W}$, $V\tilde{T}$, and $T\tilde{S}CR$ are the min-max-normalized pedestrian waiting time, pedestrian travel time, vehicle waiting time, vehicle travel time and traffic light switching conflict rate, respectively:

$$\tilde{x}_i = \frac{x_i - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)}. \quad (6)$$

The weight allocation is as follows: $\alpha = 0.1$, $\beta = 0.1$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\delta = 0.1$, and $\epsilon = 0.6$. It emphasizes safety while still considering efficiency. Specifically, this CPS treats the traffic efficiency of vehicles (VW and VT) and pedestrians (PW and PT) equally important, while still puts the safety (0.6) more important than efficiency (0.4) overall.

Fig. 6. Composite Performance Scores for each traffic control method. SafeCrossLight achieves the lowest CPS, indicating the best tradeoff between efficiency and safety.

CPS results in Fig. 6 confirm that SafeCrossLight achieves the best tradeoff between efficiency and safety, outperforming traditional controllers and recent DRL-based approaches.

VI. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this study, we proposed SafeCrossLight, a deep reinforcement learning based traffic signal control approach that jointly considers both traffic efficiency and pedestrian safety in an urban intersection scenario. It uses a composite reward balances traffic efficiency and pedestrian safety. To further enhance real-world applicability, we introduced a novel two-stage signal transition mechanism. Instead of inserting a generic all-red phase during signal switching, our approach uses a structured phase sequence that first stops pedestrian movement, then safely transitions vehicle flows using yellow light buffers. Besides, the agent uses a D3QN to stabilise training and improve value estimation. In SUMO simulations, SafeCrossLight significantly reduced traffic light switching conflict while maintaining competitive vehicle delays, outperforming fixed-time controllers and recently DRL methods such as SafeLight-R and IntelliLight. Overall, this work demonstrates the potential of integrating DRL with safety factors to realize intelligent, adaptive, and more pedestrian-safe urban traffic control systems.

In the future, we will extend the approach to other VRUs (e.g. cyclists, scooter riders) and explore control strategies

for multiple interconnected intersections to move toward a scalable, real-world deployment of safety-aware signal control.

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